

Connected forestry - Proposed method for impact assessment of 5G/IoT enabled solutions

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Abstract: Currently, telco operators are experiencing decline in revenues and therefore exploring new business opportunities through innovative digital solutions directed towards industry and the public sector. Previous research on digitalization has focused on urban communities and smart cities and less on rural areas, where the digital divide is more frequent. The EU wants to revitalize local communities through enhanced connectivity-based solutions for businesses, farmers, institutions, and families. Eliminating the digital divide in rural communities is vital if we want to fully draw on the effects of digitalization with respect to increased efficiency and reduced climate and environmental impact. The Horizon Europe project COMNECT is such a vehicle for the revitalization of rural industries in five countries in Europe, including Norway which hosts the connected forestry living lab. This article proposes a method for assessing the social and economic impacts of connectivity-based solutions such as fifth generation (5G) mobile networks and the Internet of Things on the most important steps of the forestry value chain. The method proposes assessment of expected impacts early in the development process through trials of protocepts/proofs of concepts/minimum viable products in laboratory environments prior to more extensive field trials in the intended environments. The proposed method is novel and applicable to the assessment of the impacts of digitalization beyond the forestry industry.

Keywords: *Wireless communication, Internet of Things, 5G, Rural areas, Environment/Socioeconomic assessment*

I. INTRODUCTION

The general trend in the telco industry experience is the slowing of revenue growth [1]. To mitigate this trend the industry is seeking revenues from products and services beyond the traditional network services, often applying design thinking and lean/agile innovation process methodologies [1]. Cooper [2] claims that co-creation with stakeholder groups external to the project avoids the unnecessary redesign of prototypes (proofs of concepts [POC's]/minimum

viable products [MVP's]). Digital product/service solutions are often realized through business ecosystems with stakeholders from academia and industry, often referred to as triple helix models [3].

Fifth generation (5G) mobile networks and the Internet of Things (IoT) serve to enable technologies for digitalization. Recent technological development has resulted in powerful micro controller units (MCUs) in small formats at low cost. Sensors are also becoming smaller and cheaper (and there is a sensor for everything, temperature, position, motion, air quality, humidity, vibration, etc.). Dedicated low-power IoT networks are being deployed, resulting in longer-lasting batteries. Large datasets collected using sensors can be handled by artificial intelligence (AI) and mined for value. As the fifth generation and mobile communication technology, 5G offers faster network response time, increases the throughput of end-user application data, and consumes less power than 4G. In addition, it will be able to support 1 million IoT devices per square kilometer [4]. Various network technologies support wireless communication from devices and sensors. Low power wide area (LPWA) technologies are dedicated IoT protocols in 4G mobile network were we also find LoraWan and NarrowBand IoT (NB-IoT) which is a commercial offering. The majority of the 66 commercial IoT networks launched thus far worldwide are NB-IoT networks, according to GSMA, an association of mobile network operators. In January 2020, NB-IoT reached the milestone of 100 million connections globally. However, subscription and traffic costs are dropping quickly. Deutsche Telecom in Germany recently offered a IoT subscription for a one-off cost of 10 euros over 10 years, including 500 MB and 250 SMSs.

The forestry industry is one of the oldest industries in Norway, typically located in rural areas of the country. In 2020, the total volume of logging was 12 million cubic meters [5]. The forestry industry is a highly relevant industry in the context of society's

current focus on increased sustainability. Demand is high for the correct type and amount of timber. Precise and sustainable forestry practices are also emphasized now to protect biotopes and cultural monuments. The Norwegian programme for the endorsement of forest certification (PEFC) provides national forest certification systems tailored to local conditions [6]. The forestry value chain consists of several steps spanning 60-80 years or more. The main activities are planting, caring, thinning and logging. In the planting stage, new trees are substituting those previously logged. Almost 40 million trees were planted in Norway in 2021 [7]. The caring stage involves cutting down surrounding trees that are too densely planted. The thinning stage includes removing trees that are unsuitable for further growth and profit. Logging is carried out according to the specifications (length and quality) from the client. After logging, the timber is brought by timber trucks to the sawmills, where they are cut into different shapes and sizes or further processed into pulpwood or paper. The value of a log increases approximately 10 times before it reaches the customer as a product [7].

A literature review shows previous research findings on digitalization related to certain steps in the forestry lifecycle, e.g., locating automatic forestry machines (harvesters) in Polen using satellites [8], 5G based remote steering of forest machines (forwarders), hauling the logs to a roadside landing in Sweden (for further transport with timber trucks) [9] as well as forestry data management in Lithuania, using drones [10]. The background for all these research studies is the lack of enhanced connectivity solutions (5G/IoT) in rural communities.

The research question guiding this article pertains to assessing the effects of digitalization on the forestry industry: How can socioeconomic impacts of 5G/IoT-based solutions be assessed at an early stage of the innovation process?

II. METHODOLOGY

We deployed interviews, workshops, and surveys as data collection methods to address our research question (see Table 1). The interviews and workshops were oriented towards stakeholders in Norway's Connected Forestry Living Lab (LL) in a selected region of the country. Three face-to-face workshops have so far been performed together with twenty forestry industry participants. The objectives are to identify 1) the main stakeholder pain-points today and how new digital solutions could help address these challenges, 2) which types of business, social, and environmental impacts they expect digitalized

solutions to offer them, even if not fully materialized yet, and 3) which stakeholders roles and business models were the most relevant for a telco to adopt when implementing 5G/IoT use case solutions.

TABLE I. DESCRIPTION OF DATA SOURCES

Approach	Data sources
Online survey (Fall 2024)	Assessment of use case solutions (PoC/MVP) through online survey feedback from forestry stakeholders in multiple regions in Norway
Workshop (Fall 2023)	Workshop with forestry value chain stakeholders in southeast of Norway to gather feedback on use case solutions (PoC/MVP) and business models
Interview (Spring 2023)	Interviews (Teams) with individual LL stakeholders to uncover current needs and challenges in forestry value chain

Going forward, an online survey study on expected impacts will include additional regions beyond the LL stakeholders located in southeast of Norway. The online survey aims to gather feedback on the expected impacts of lab/field-tested digital use case solutions (PoC/MVP) for a larger sample of stakeholders. The survey questionnaire was pre-tested in spring 2024 and will be launched online in fall 2024. Using multiple methods or data sources helps us develop a comprehensive understanding of the research phenomenon, also referred to as triangulation [11]. The way the stakeholders were recruited to the LL is often referred to as strategic selections [11]. The data gathered through interviews and workshops were documented in minutes that later were confirmed by the stakeholders, to enhance reliability and validity [12]. Finally, all the data were analysed on a case-by-case basis. According to Larson and Larson [13], a use case describes how stakeholders use a system (e.g. technology) to perform a task that results in the achievement of an overall objective. In the context of COMTECT's Connected Forestry LL [14], the use cases are recognized as situations where 1) 5G/IoT-based solutions are applied, 2) each stakeholder have a personal interest in the situation, and 3) the expected impact of making use of these solutions in their companies/organizations is assessed.

III. FINDINGS

Here we present a method (data collection and analysis) for how socioeconomic impact of 5G/IoT-based solutions can be assessed at an early stage of the innovation process. The assessment of these impacts is grounded in an agile development process illustrated in Fig. 1 [15] [16]. This process involves four steps, and the use cases are here looked upon as concrete situations/events, where one or alternative solutions may be applied, and where individuals hold stakes in the situations/events [17].

Fig. 1: Agile development process phases

The development process starts with use case descriptions (1) with the mapping of pain points, needs, and requirements for value chain stakeholders in the LL. The next step involves the design and trials of use case connectivity solutions (2). This includes specifying and testing the PoCs/MVPs of connectivity-enabled solutions in small -and large-scale trials. Based on the trials of the prototypes, the impacts (with respect to performance, socioeconomics, and environment) can be assessed (3). These tests can include prototypes on different technology readiness levels [18], from mere protocepts [2] on TRL levels 2 and 3 to more mature solutions in real world environment, i.e. TRL levels 6 and 7. If the trial results do not meet requirements, the solution and set-up undergo iterative redesign processes. Finally, when the results meet requirements, the business models are designed (4). Here the aim is to exploit the expected impact that connectivity-enabled solutions have on value creation for businesses and non-commercial stakeholders. This model guides the co-creation and realization of the solution as well as distributes revenue/cost sharing among value chain stakeholders.

The socioeconomic impact is measured based on the feedback from questionnaires (face-to-face and online surveys). The structure of the questionnaire is as follows: Section 1 gathers general information about the respondent (company/organization), Section 2 ask information about the history of product/service and process innovation and collaboration with external partners, and Section 3 covers the type and degree of expected impacts from implementing 5G/IoT-enabled connectivity solutions. Roughly 20 impact factors divided into three groups are listed, where the respondent is requested to respond on the degree of impact (small, medium, high) on a scale from 1 to 6. For selected economic parameters the magnitude of the impact (e.g., 0-10% or 10 - 20%) is requested if the

respondent assigns a score of 5 or 6 to the previous question. The 5G/IoT-enabled connectivity solutions are described with text, illustrations, and videos virtualizing the use case PoC/MVP [2]. Section 5, the final section, describes the methodological approach to R&D in general (i.e. the extent of linear or agile development processes). Below, the impact groups with separate factors are presented.

Social impact assessment factors:

- *Ease of use/user experience*: This includes an enhanced user experience due to value chain stakeholders/users/consumers operating digital solutions in their work and the increased utility resulting from their use. The ease of use might be improved via information about the terrain and maps delivered from 360-degree camera streaming of images through headset displays.
- *Enhanced reputation in the community*: This involves gaining an enhanced reputation among peer actors in the industry for sustainable and health-, safety- and environmental- (HSE) friendly operations. This could also include a reputational increase among the public authorities and certification agencies through improved processes that are more in accordance with laws and regulations.
- *Increased trust in the technology in use*. This includes the belief in that the technology is not harmful to human beings (e.g. network tower radiation), in addition to trusting that data (video, voice, text, positions, etc.) are treated as confidential by operators and employees.
- *Increased digital inclusion of the community*. This involves general digital inclusion by means of access to mobile broadband in the community where the use case solutions are implemented. For the professional stakeholders, this implies an improved ability to digitalize, automate, and robotize. For the private community stakeholders this also includes increased quality of life through reduced commuting and increased use of home office alternatives.

Economic impact assessment factors:

- *Increased revenues from solutions sold*. This involves new revenues from commercialized products and services (solutions) in the industry/market for different players in the value chain. Depending on the business model, certain stakeholders play the role as a provider of a complete system/solution to the end user/customer while splitting the revenues with other vendors and providers of elements of the complete system. This also includes the customers (end users), as well as producers of

license-based revenues, as opposed to open-source and royalty-free solutions.

- *Reduced costs from solutions in use:* This refers to reduced costs spent on labor and equipment/devices on user operations as a result of digitalization/connectivity solutions and improved technology. This could also include reduced penalty and insurance cost for operating accordance to regulations and certifications. Introducing drones as a substitute for fire guarding after logging operations reduces the need for manual labor, i.e replacing human operators with machines. Introducing “plug-and-play” methods ways of implementing solutions also contributes to the reduction of costs.
- *Reduced time spent:* This includes time reductions per operator/employee or per process/steps related to operating the product/service applied by the end users. Examples includes online maintenances or supervisions that reduces time spent on travelling to remote sites.

Environmental impact assessment factors:

- *Reduced consumption of resources.* This pertains to different types of limited resources used by stakeholders, such as the reduced use of pesticides by forest owners, and decreased use of energy and materials by forest machine operators in accordance with PEFC regulations.
- *Reduced contamination of the forest:* This relates to the extent of CO2 emissions and waste resulting from thinning and logging activities in the forest. Based on maps with information about assignments, smart routes can be designed to reduce CO2 emissions and waste from activities. This is also relevant to the factors mentioned above and below.
- *Less intervention in forest flora and fauna:* This group of factors includes less abrasion of the forest floor and vegetation, (e.g. by forest machine owners) improved conservation of insect/animal and plant species diversity, and enhanced preservation of cultural heritage sites, such as ancient settlements.

The online survey questionnaire will be distributed to respondents in all regions of Norway, not only the southeast region where we initially focused our stakeholder interviews. We will concentrate on involving two stakeholder groups in the online study: 1) four main forest owner associations in Norway and 2) the national association of forest machine operators (MEF). The former stakeholder group comprises approximately 100 forest managers from the four major associations. The latter stakeholder group comprises approximately 130 managers from the MEF

association. Our contact persons representing the respective associations will distribute the online survey link to the respondents via emails. Before launching the survey in earnest, a pilot is performed on a selected group of informants (approximately 20 individuals). Based on feedback from this pre-test, we have already updated the online survey questionnaire. The individual LL stakeholders are here responsible for adapting and executing their online survey according to their national regulations and guidelines. In the case of Norway, a confirmation from the Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research is necessary before launching the survey nationally.

The data from the online survey will be analyzed using both qualitative and quantitative methods. The distribution of responses to each question is relevant, and if the sample becomes big enough, statistical analysis may also be applied to validate significant success factors/drivers for impact. We also aim to use the qualitative comparative analysis (QCA) method for the analysis of data from the online survey. Although QCA is often associated with intensive qualitative engagement and the use of in-depth case knowledge (a case-oriented approach), it can also use large data samples with less weight on qualitative insights [19]. One specific QCA model could be deployed to investigate the roles of 5 relevant conditions and their effect on the socioeconomic impacts (benefits) of the implemented connectivity solution. Conditions that might be explored (refer to factors from the online survey template) include: 1) Level of collaboration with external partners, 2) Innovation orientation in the department, 3) Attitude toward the adoption of new technologies, 4) Competences in the new technology implemented and 5) Level of support on the new technology implemented. See Table 2 for an example of how the results show that three different routes can lead to high levels of social benefits from using the new technology, and how certain factors must be in place to achieve a successful outcome (i.e. impact).

TABLE II: EXAMPLE OF QCA RESULTS

Route	Collaboration with external partners	Innovation orientation	Attitude toward the adoption of new technologies	Technology competence	Technology support
1	●		●	●	
2	○	●	●	●	
3		●	●	○	●

Black circle "●" – has to be in place. White circle "○" – should not be in place. Blank cell indicate an irrelevant

Table 2 shows that a positive attitude towards new connectivity solutions is necessary for all routes to succeed. Moreover, if the necessary competences are not in place, technical support is required. Overall, QCA is a relevant and useful method for evaluating

the effectiveness of new connectivity solutions to achieve high levels of positive impact.

Two use case PoCs/MVPs/protocepts were presented in the survey using illustrations and text description (see Fig. 2). These use cases were identified through the initial interviews and workshops and sets the scene for the respondent to assess the type and level social, economic, and environmental impact from applying these 5G/IoT-enabled solutions in their organizations

Fig. 2: 5G/IoT enabled case protocepts/PoCs/MVPs.

1. **Remote operation support and digital assistance.** Through the use of virtual reality (VR) glasses, computer displays, or mobile terminals, the operator can be supervised by a remote expert for more precise and efficient thinning and logging activities. Cameras mounted on the forest machine, in addition to information from drones, will also support the expert in ensuring optimal decision making by the operator. The expert can also represent the machine vendor in cases of machine repair/maintenance, or even a representative of the local government when logging in the proximity of sensitive areas/cultural monuments.
2. **Complex situation awareness service.** With sensors (soil, air, etc.) and drones (with infrared cameras), the operator can be notified (through VR glasses, computer display, or mobile terminals) on access to fires in relation to thinning, logging, and transport activities performed during dry seasons. This real-time information can also be distributed to the mobile terminals of emergency personnel (police, firefighters, and medics) to coordinate their joint efforts in responding to a fire that spreads to a larger area or other emergency situations such as landslides or floods. Drone cameras can also perform object counting and assess forest health.

To realize our two use case solutions, high-resolution video cameras will be deployed on forestry machinery that will stream live videos to the remote experts to facilitate their support. A high-quality private 5G network (consisting of a mobile trailer with a 5G core, 5G radio, and edge server) will be required to transmit live video streams from cameras mounted on forest machinery to experts located elsewhere. Moreover, drones will be used to surveil the forest and send video/image feeds to the edge server, and using AI and machine learning algorithms, appropriate actions will be taken based on decisions. Simultaneously, IoT sensors positioned on the forest floor will employ a 5G network to transmit data to the edge server. The Raspberry Pi console, located at the far edge, will receive the IoT data. Immediate processing will occur at this far-edge device to identify critical patterns by means of the combination of IoT data, such as detecting fires or unexpectedly low humidity.

IV. DISCUSSION

The proposed method for socioeconomic impact assessment is adapted to 5G/IoT-based solutions at an early stage of technology readiness. Vik et al. [20] introduce the balanced TRL tool/framework with four additional dimensions (group of factors) beyond the technology readiness level, namely the market readiness level (MRL), regulatory readiness level (RRL), acceptance readiness level (ARL), and organizational readiness level (ORL). Each of these dimensions refers to nine levels (1-9) of maturity, each with an individual meaning. For the MRL, the 1 level corresponds to “Hunch of a market need,” while 9 corresponds to “Market confirms stability/growth.” For the ORL, the 1 corresponds to “Technology represents a fundamental break with existing work processes or organization,” and 9 corresponds to “Technology works seamlessly with existing technology.” For the ARL, 1 refers to “Technology is or will be seen as illegitimate or unacceptable,” while 9 corresponds to “Technology is generally accepted/applauded.” Finally, for the RRL, 1 corresponds to “Legal and/or regulatory aspects of the technology is unpredictable or unknown.” The balanced TRL framework focuses on technologies applied within the agricultural sector (drones, robots, etc.) as well as for livestock agriculture (cattle and sheep with no fencing). Data from the questions related to the different dimensions are plotted in a pentagon - the more mature the levels are, the more closely the scores follow the outer line of the pentagon. This balanced TRL tool/framework is a candidate for application when analyzing final impact results from

the two selected use cases in COMMECT's Connected Forestry LL.

Upham et al. [21] argues that assessment of social acceptance should be performed by a mix of stakeholders (public/private, individual/professional). Vik et al.'s [20] balanced readiness level assessment tool contains multiple dimensions and factors. The acceptance readiness dimension captures whether individuals and communities welcome the novel technology or regard it as controversial. This feedback adds insight to the narrow focus on technological aspects from the TRL dimension. Previous research show that factors such as utility, trust, employee well-being, and sustainability, impacts the use of the new technologies and innovations such as cloud technology or e-commerce [22] as well as peoples' intention to adopt technology such as mobile banking [19]. These factors are vital to assess in the initial steps of research and innovation projects to avoid delays and reduced uptake of the technology-based solutions. The unified theory of acceptance and use of technology (UTAUT) extends the perspective on adoption of new technology compared to the individual user behavior focus on the technology acceptance model (TAM) [23]. However, they both lack a systematic and holistic approach to the assessment of novel technology-based solutions on the use case level [24]. According to Cooper [25] economic factors are vital to include when assessing impact from new product innovation-based use cases. This involves both quantitative factors such as profit, pay-back time, and market share as well as qualitative factors such as policy alignment, unique offering, and sales potential [26]. Zhang and Doll [27] suggests two additional groups of project outcome factors beyond the economic factor when assessing impact: product (achievement, expenses, etc.) and process (development time, partnership, etc.). Vidueira et al. [28] and Passani [29] stress that both economic and environmental impact factors are necessary to include in their ex-ante assessments of European rural development programmes (RDPs) from 2007 to 2013: (1) economic growth; (2) employment creation; (3) labour productivity; (4) reversing biodiversity decline; (5) maintenance of high nature value farming and forestry areas; (6) improvement in water quality; and (7) contributing to combating climate change.

QCA has been successfully adopted in the management literature recently [30]. Overall, QCA is a flexible and powerful method for examining complex relationships between conditions and outcomes. Identifying necessary and sufficient conditions and multiple causal recipes can provide valuable insights into how different conditions interact

and influence outcomes of interest [31]. It allows researchers to consider multiple factors and their interactions, which can be crucial for understanding complex technologies such as those investigated in the COMMECT project. By identifying necessary and sufficient conditions and multiple causal recipes, QCA can provide valuable insights into how to optimize the use of technologies and ensure the best possible outcomes for all forestry stakeholders involved. With a large sample response from the online survey, significant cause-effect analysis could be conducted using the statistical analysis method. A subset of the sample responses could also be candidates for in-depth OCA analysis.

V. CONCLUSION

In studies of rural communities, digitalization in rural communities is inadequately treated compared to research in cities and urban communities. This article presents a method for assessment of socioeconomic and environmental impacts from the perspective of new digital solutions in the forestry industry in the early stages of the innovation process to avoid costly modifications at a later stage. Although the technology readiness level (TRL) is low compared to real life tests, valuable stakeholder feedback will be provided through small interviews and a large sample online survey. This article suggests ways of collecting and analyzing data from rural stakeholders engaged in the development of 5G/IoT-enhanced solutions. The different factors that were grouped into the three impact dimensions are recruited from state-of-the-art research findings and provides a holistic view of the outcome of digitalization in the forestry industry. To mitigate the lack of ready to use digital products/services at the time of the assessment, detailed text/illustrations/videos of the 5G/IoT enabled protocept/PoC/MVP were developed. This corresponds to the findings from Nesse et al. [32] demonstrating similar use of protocepts in other 5G use cases. After piloting a lean start-up methodology in these projects, the stakeholders reported the equal importance of the technological performance, commercial output, social acceptance (including environmental friendliness), when validating the 5G/IoT-based forestry solutions in the early stages of the development process. Descriptive and correlation-based analysis methods, together with qualitative methods such as QCA, are recommended for survey data analysis. The results presented in this article covers the Norwegian forestry industry; further studies should also involve other regions and industries.

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